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Skin Self-Examination in Melanoma Prevention: An Integrative Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Melanoma, the most serious type of skin cancer, arises from pigment-producing cells in the epidermis. Individuals with a history of melanoma are at high risk of recurrence, making skin self-examination (SSE) a crucial strategy for reducing mortality. Early detection of preclinical melanomas by laypersons or healthcare professionals is possible through visual inspection. Dermatological education for SSE, especially for high-risk patients, can aid in early identification of clinical signs for more accurate interventions. **Objective:** To analyze the scientific literature on melanoma, focusing on disease prevention through SSE. **Methodology:** An integrative literature review was conducted using the Virtual Health Library (Medline) database and the following Health Sciences Descriptors (DeCS/MeSH) in combination: (Melanoma) AND (Self-examination). Inclusion criteria were: full-text articles published in the last 5 years, in English or Portuguese, that addressed SSE as the main topic. Articles not meeting the eligibility criteria or the proposed theme were excluded. Of the 36 articles found, 10 were selected for analysis. **Results:** The studies indicated that individuals with a history of melanoma have recurrence rates of around 5%, highlighting the high risk of recurrence. Melanoma has a relatively long average development time, allowing patients to notice skin changes in their daily lives. It is essential that there is education on lesion recognition through SSE, as well as mobilization of healthcare professionals to ensure a skin examination routine. The studies demonstrated that SSE applied with adequate knowledge and documentation can reduce melanoma morbidity and mortality. Support from third parties, such as family members and spouses, was also found to be relevant in lesion assessment. However, the low frequency of SSE performance was the main obstacle to early detection of signs. Several psychosocial, economic, and educational factors associated with melanoma patients who use SSE can negatively influence their motivation and ability to perform the checks. **Conclusion:** In summary, the use of protocols that encourage documentation and active search for skin lesions by melanoma survivors has been shown to provide more favorable prognoses and early treatment when compared to, especially, individuals without prior contact with the disease or unaware of SSE. On the other hand, adherence to screening is the major challenge for this practice. This ranges from unwillingness and difficulty in examining certain parts of the body to anxiety triggers arising from monitoring skin blemishes.

KEYWORDS: Melanoma; Skin self-examination; Prevention.

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